

Physico-chemical characters and quality assessment of some soil in the region of Khedi village of Amravati district (Maharashtra State), India

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Abstract : Soil testing is a sound scientific tool to assess inherent power of soil to supply plant nutrients. Five samples were collected from the Khedi village (farmers field) of Warud Taluka in Amravati district belongs to (Maharashtra State), India were selected for present investigation in the month of February-March 2013. Moisture pH, calcium, organic carbon, magnesium, zinc, electric conductance, calcium carbonate, TDS, nitrogen, phosphorous, potassium, alkalinity soil parameters were analyzed. It was found that there was a marked variation in nutrients and parameters of various sample point in different farmers field.

Keywords : Quality assessment, physico-chemical characters, soil in Khedi village of Amravati.

Introduction

The soil cover is a major interface between agriculture and environment. It represents the difference between survival and extinction for most land-based life. The quality and health of soil determine agricultural sustainability and environmental quality which jointly determines plant, animal and human health. Soil testing is the only way to determine the available nutrient status in soil and the only way we can develop specific fertilizer recommendations. Physico-chemical properties of four farm site soils in area surrounding Rajkot, Gujarat, India¹ have been reported. Solanki reported² physico-chemical analysis with reference to seasonal changes in soils of Victoria Park Reserve Forest, Bhavnagar (Gujarat). Microbiological and physico-chemical studies of soil near Bhokar of Maharashtra material and methods³. Electrical conductivity and dielectric constant as predictors of chemical properties and available nutrients in the soil⁴. pH of soil of Majalgaon command area (Jayakwadi project stage-III), India⁵. Considerable research work has been done regarding the study of nutrients from various types of soil in Maharashtra as well as in India⁶⁻⁸. Perveen *et al.*⁹ have studied micronutrient status of soils and their relationship with various physico-chemical properties. Physico-chemical studies of soil collected from Eastern part of Pune have been reported¹⁰. Physico-chemical assessment

of soil in Rajura Bazar¹¹ in Amravati district of Maharashtra (India) but the investigation of physico-chemical characters and quality assessment of some soil in the region of Khedi village in Warud Tahsil of Amravati district in Maharashtra, India was still lacking hence this work have been done for the same.

Experimental

(A) *Study area* : Khedi village is a village in Warud Tahsil in Amravati District of Maharashtra State, India. It belongs to Amravati Division, this area is well known for oranges, turmeric and chillies. The sources of water for this area is of well and tube well. It is located at bottom of Satpuda ranges. Soil analysis provides information which can be used to improve soil fertility through management, which gives us more yield.

(B) *Sample collection* : Five samples were collected from the study area (farmers field) in the month of February 2013. Soil samples were collected randomly at 0 to 15 cm and 15 to 30 cm depths with five plots, five samples from each plot respectively, in well sterilised polythene pouches.

Soil sample were collected from following farmers fields :

(1) Soil sample 1 (MVP-1) was collected from Mr. Sukhadevrao Ande's field.

(2) Soil sample 2 (MVP-2) was collected from Mr. Shridhar Sawarkar's field.

(3) Soil sample 3 (MVP 1-3) was collected from Mr. Jaydev Wanjari's field.

(4) Soil sample 4 (MVP-4) was collected from Mr. Wasudevrao Moghe's field.

(5) Soil sample 5 (MVP-5) was collected from Dr. Deshmukh's field.

(C) *Physico-chemical analysis of soil samples* : Reagents used for this research work were AR grade and chemicals other than reagent are LR grade manufactured by S.D. fine, LOBA and Merck. The soil samples were dried for about 24 h and grinded more finely.

Methods used for estimation of various parameters are,

(1) Determination of moisture : By weighting method.

(2) Determination of pH : By digital pH meter.

(3) Determination of electric conductance : By conductometer.

(4) Determination of organic carbon : By titration method.

(5) Determination of magnesium (Mg) : By EDTA titration method.

(6) Determination of calcium (Ca) : By titration method.

(7) Determination of TDS : Total dissolved solid were estimated TDS meter.

(8) Determination of zinc (Zn) : Atomic adsorption spectroscopy.

(9) Determination of nitrogen (N) : By titration method.

(10) Determination of phosphorous (P) : By titration method.

(11) Determination of potassium (K) : By flame photometry.

(12) Determination of calcium carbonate (CaCO₃) : By titration method.

(13) Determination of colour of soil : Viewing soil.

(14) Determination of alkalinity : By titration method.

Results and discussion

Moisture : The moisture content value ranges from 1–6%. It is clear from the result that soil sample MVP-4 only 1% moisture which is very less as compared to sample MVP-1, MVP-2, MVP-3 and MVP-5.

pH : pH was observed in the range 7.14–8.10. The soil sample MVP-1, MVP-3, MVP-4 and MVP-5 is very slightly alkaline sample and MVP-2 sample is medium alkaline.

Calcium : The calcium content in the soil sample ranged from 0.160–0.248. It is seen that soil sample MVP-1, MVP-2, MVP-3, MVP-4 have less amount of calcium content as compared to MVP-5.

Organic carbon : Organic carbon values were recorded

Table 1. Nutrients and physico-chemical parameters of soil samples

Sr. no.	Parameters	MVP-1 (Soil sample-1)	MVP-2 (Soil sample-2)	MVP-3 (Soil sample-3)	MVP-4 (Soil sample-4)	MVP-5 (Soil sample-5)
1.	Moisture (%)	6.00	6.00	4.50	1.00	1.70
2.	pH	7.98	8.10	7.95	7.58	7.14
3.	Calcium (%)	0.200	0.208	0.160	0.184	0.248
4.	Organic carbon (%)	1.95	2.31	2.01	1.65	1.27
5.	Magnesium (%)	0.121	0.126	0.097	0.112	0.151
6.	Zinc (ppm)	1.19	2.09	1.49	1.79	2.38
7.	Electric conductance	1.94	0.67	0.53	0.45	0.70
8.	Calcium carbonate (CaCO ₃) (%)	6.25	7.00	6.25	5.25	6.25
9.	TDS	195	171	135	146	56
10.	Nitrogen (kg/hect)	256	268	249	301	248
11.	Phosphorous (kg/hect)	28.5	26.5	29.5	26.5	21.00
12.	Potassium (kg/hect)	648	548	648	398	498
13.	Colour	Faint black	Faint black	Black	Brown	Brown
14.	Alkalinity	194	242	145	97	145

in the range of 1.27–2.31%. The soil sample MVP-4 and MVP-5, has less organic carbon and sample MVP-1, have moderate and MVP-2 and MVP-3, have percent of organic carbon.

Magnesium : The magnesium content in the soil sample ranged from 0.097–0.151%. It is seen that soil sample MVP-3, MVP-4 has less amount of magnesium. Soil sample MVP-1 and MVP-2 have moderate amount of magnesium. Soil sample MVP-5 high percent of magnesium.

Zinc : Zinc content in soil sample ranges from 1.19–2.38, it seen that soil sample MVP-1, MVP-3 and MVP-4 have less amount of zinc content as compared to soil sample MVP-2 and MVP-5.

Electro conductance : Electro conductance values ranged from 0.45–1.94 μS . It is seen that soil sample MVP-1 has more electric conductivity as compared sample MVP-2, MVP-3, MVP-4 and MVP-5.

Calcium carbonate : Calcium carbonate value ranges from 5.25–7.00, it seen that soil sample MVP-4 have less amount of calcium chloride soil samples MVP-1, MVP-3 and MVP-5 have same amount calcium chloride and soil sample MVP-2 have high amount of calcium chloride.

Total dissolved solid (TDS) : The TDS in soil sample ranges from 56–195%, it is seen that soil sample MVP-5 has less percent of TDS, soil samples MVP-2, MVP-3 and MVP-4 has moderate percent of TDS and MVP-1 has high percent of TDS.

Nitrogen : Nitrogen content in the soil sample ranges from 248–301 kg/hect. The soil MVP-4 has high nitrogen content as compared to soil samples MVP-1, MVP-2, MVP-3 and MVP-5.

Phosphorous : Phosphorous content in the soil sample ranged between 21.00–29.5 kg/hect. The soil sample MVP-5 have less phosphorous content as compared to soil samples MVP-1, MVP-2, MVP-3 and MVP-4.

Potassium : Potassium content in the soil sample ranged between 398–648 kg/hect. The soil sample MVP-4 have less potassium content as compared to soil samples MVP-1, MVP-2, MVP-3 and MVP-5.

Colour : Soil samples MVP-4 and MVP-5 were brown in colour and soil samples MVP-1, MVP-2 faint black, soil sample MVP-3 was black in colour.

Alkalinity : Alkalinity was observed in the range between 97–242%. It is seen that soil sample MVP-2 has high amount of alkalinity and soil samples MVP-1, MVP-3, MVP-5 moderate alkalinity MVP-4 has less alkalinity.

Conclusion

All nutrient concentrations were available in sufficient amount for growth of plant and soil organisms. Soil is fertile but also it is slightly alkaline in nature. Magnesium has been considered as non toxic to human at all concentration expected in soil. The primary nutrient zinc and micronutrient phosphorous concentrations were available in sufficient amount for growth of plant and soil organisms.

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